

Book review of “Faire Référence. La Construction de l’Autorité dans le Discours des Institutions” by Claire Oger, Paris 2021

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Abstract

Book review of “Faire Référence. La Construction de l’Autorité dans le Discours des Institutions” [Making Reference. The Construction of Authority in the Discourse of Institutions] by Claire Oger, Paris, EHESS – Éditions de l’École des hautes études en sciences sociales 2021, 400 pp.

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Keywords

institutional discourse, discourse of authority, authoritarian discourse, discursive neutralization, discursive contestation

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Introduction

Over the nine chapters that constitute this work, apart from the introduction and conclusion, Claire Oger analyses the discursive dimension which “lies at the heart of authority, which is the key to its functioning and enables one to address the topic of its efficiency” (p. 13, free translation from the French original). Along this path, centered on the discourse of institutions, the author questions the nature and the foundations of the discursive authority, the process by which it is established, built and sometimes disputed, its faces and its challenges, including the greater challenge expounded throughout the book which is that of distinguishing types of frequently confused discourses: the authoritarian discourse and the discourse of authority.

The first two chapters are devoted precisely to explaining the concept of authority, of how it can be considered, cross-checking its lexical usages, definitions, manifestations in speeches, and differences vis-à-vis neighboring notions such as power, domination, conditioning or legitimacy. The author demarcates it as “a particular form of credibility, a mode of intervention as well, legitimized in a specific public space (intellectual or scientific controversy, judicial bodies), and an ability to influence and guide the discourse of others” (p. 20, free translation from the French original). She then analyses its different forms, from personal authority to institutional authority in which, by contrast to the marks of subjectivity of the former, the technical-administrative function prevails, qualified by an institutional approach of the *ethos*, more closely linked to the enunciation than to the individual speaker.

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The third chapter explores concepts associated to authority, such as those of author, auctorality and *auctoritas*, intersecting the Middle Ages and the Renaissance with the transformations in the manufacturing of texts and in the assignment of the enunciative responsibility, to focus on recent practices and works and in the extension of the polyphonic authority to analyze, for instance, the circulation of authorized statements, or the values of truth and authenticity that permeate the reference practices. These are issues to which the author returns in the fourth chapter, this time in connection with the transformations brought about by communication and digital devices.

The fifth chapter addresses the scientific discourse, taking the academic writing as an illustration of the interweaving of the different forms of authority: which does not constitute a universe of demonstration or of rational argumentation closed in on itself, which is traversed by naturalizations and common sense, in which authority that is articulated with the ‘scientific’ truths opens up to the question of a broader circulation of the scientific discourse, including its mobilization at the service of political argumentation, of public action or of experts’ discourses. This topic is resumed in the following three chapters: in the sixth, in which centrality is given to the notion of performativity, to highlight the importance of the recognition awarded the speaker and his/her credibility in the construction of the discursive authority; in the seventh, which deals with the status and nature of the discourse of experts and its place in the formulation or in the steering of public action; and finally, in the eighth chapter, devoted to the topic of the neutral/of the discursive neutralization. Oger shows how the discourse of institutions, as a discourse of authority, is at the same time the result and the main operator of the neutralization of the

tensions that pervade a political body or a specific community, and of which institutions propose a fictional, unified representation, whereby the discursive authority manifests itself primarily by forms of enunciative deletion and discursive neutralization.

The ninth and final chapter explores the features that build the discourse of authority, trust and commitment, in its differences from the authoritarian discourse, which aims above all at obedience, drawing a divide between the acceptable part of authority in the discourse of institutions and possible deviations towards abuse of power, brutality or violence.

This is a work which, combining the contributions from different disciplines (sociology, political science, history, language sciences, anthropology, information and communication sciences), is not limited to the theoretical framework of the topics it covers, which it does in detail. Rather, it presents and also refers the reader to a broad set of empirical research works, albeit mostly produced within the sphere of the francophone world. Although the fact that it is written in French and was published four years ago may limit its potential readership, the advantages pointed out above make us consider that it can be a must-read for students, researchers and others interested in issues related to the discursive functioning and the mechanisms of construction of authority in institutional discourses. Moreover, it is written in a very readable style.

For its topical nature, we would highlight the author’s analysis of the discourse of authority in its articulation with the transformations generated by communication and digital devices, their circulation conditions and biases, including the misunderstandings in the definition of borders between authority and visibility or notoriety. Within this context, we share with the readers of *Language, Discourse & Society* the reference to the concept of *authority-dispositif*: imbued of an authority similar to discursive authority, shifts and materializes itself in a panoply of devices (e.g., websites, participation platforms, toolkits) and takes on the roles of a discourse of authority when, in the invocation of its neutrality and purely technical or information functions, it exposes a political will and the imposition of implicit norms.

Nevertheless, assuming that the discourse of authority is that which is capable of imposing itself as a mode of evidence, of neutrality and of consensus and, at the same time, as deterrent of questioning and discussion, the book leaves open an important topic: between the discourse of authority and the authoritarian discourse, whether and under which conditions counter-discourse can be constructed.